
**VIRTUAL LEARNING TOOLS IN CLASSROOMS AND
UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS' ACQUISITION OF 21ST CENTURY
SKILLS IN NIGERIA.**

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Abstract

This study determines the influence of virtual learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills in Nigeria. Three research objectives and hypotheses were formulated and postulated to guide the study and descriptive research design was used. The population consisted of the entire 10,152 undergraduate students in two institutions. A sample of 985 students was selected from the population through multi-stage and simple random sampling techniques. Researchers-developed instrument titled "Virtual Learning Tools and 21st Century Skills Questionnaire" (VLT21stCSQ) was used in gathering data. The face validity of the instrument was carried out, and the reliability coefficient .79 of the instrument was determined using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistical tool after a trial test. Data collected were analysed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Findings established a significant influence of virtual learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills from University of Uyo and Abia State University. Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that there is a shift in instructional delivery, students' participation and assessment toward technological approach through virtual learning. Since virtual learning is one of the most important advancements in attempting to rethink the effectiveness of education in all over the world, it is recommended, among others, that teachers should use the virtual tools applications such that the students enjoy the experience. Students may find it useful to know that their teachers are supportive and willing to work with them in a positive competitive environment.

Key words: Kahoot, Edmodo, Google Classroom, 21st century skills.

Introduction

Today, as never before, meeting our society's challenges demands educational excellence. Reinvigorating the economy, achieving energy independence with alternative technologies and green jobs, and strengthening our health care system require a skilled populace that is ready for the critical challenges we face. There is a widespread consensus, however, that our education systems are failing to adequately prepare all students with the essential 21st century knowledge and skills necessary to succeed in life, career and citizenship.

A 21st century education is about giving students the skills they need to succeed in this new world, and helping them grow the confidence to practice those skills. With so much information readily available to them, 21st century skills focus more on making sense of that information, sharing and using it in smart ways (The North American Council for Online Learning and the Partnership for 21st Century Skills, 2006). Obviously, teaching in the 21st century is altogether a different phenomenon; never before could learning be happening the way it is now—everywhere, all the time, on any possible topic, supporting any possible learning style or preference (Palmer, 2015).

This is an exciting and challenging time for teachers as the nature of teaching is changing. In an effort to transform themselves into exemplary teachers, many programs are becoming more entrepreneurial, recognizing new opportunities and making changes required to respond to the needs of 21st century learners. There is a shift in instructional delivery, students' participation and assessment toward technological approach through virtual learning.

Virtual learning is defined as learning that can functionally and effectively occur in the absence of traditional classroom environments (Simonson and Schlosser, 2006). Virtual Learning is one of the most important advancements in attempting to rethink the effectiveness of education in all over the world. The virtual school provides access to online, collaborative and self-paced learning environments—settings that can facilitate 21st century skills (National Education Association, 2014). These skills include communication, collaboration, critical thinking and problem solving, and creativity. 21st century skills go beyond the workplace; they can help people through the most difficult times of their life. Finding your passion, doing it well, having a sense of purpose and focus, and being able to control your own work and life are all significant steps on the path to wellbeing. 21st Century skills equip students with the competencies required for this fast-paced information age; hence, we need to prepare our students to move beyond the accumulation of content knowledge.

National Education Association (2014) asserted that 21st century skills are not restricted to cognition alone, but also the interdependencies of cognitive, social, and emotional characteristics. The emphasis of education has now shifted from reading, writing, and arithmetic to teamwork, problem solving, interpersonal skills and critical thinking to ensure success in the 21st century workplace. Today's students must be able to combine these skills with effective use of technology to succeed in current and future jobs. The full promise of virtual learning is dependent, however, on its ability to incorporate 21st century skills in its instructional design, delivery and implementation. Virtual school leaders, administrators and teachers must ensure that students who learn in virtual environments are gaining the skills necessary to compete as citizens and workers in the 21st century (Purdue University, 2018).

This is not always an easy task; and merely replicating the face-to-face methods online does not allow the learning experience to be maximized to full potential. Some fail to “make a transformational shift in their approach to teaching from one of disseminating information to one of creating learning environments where students co-construct knowledge through interactions” (Vaughan, 2010, p 61). This transition from face-to-face to a virtual method of creating a suitable learning environment for students challenges the instructor on a professional level and many are concerned about the change in roles and responsibilities, use of technology, relationships, presence, and a perceived lack of prestige (Redmond 2011).

Making virtual learning work for all students is challenging. You can have all the best tools in place, but without equitable access at home for all your students -- and adequate prep and training for yourself – it is tough to replicate a traditional, in-person learning experience. Virtual learning requires us to leverage technology like never before, but we must be careful that technology is being used intentionally as a tool to build student's skills, rather than the tools driving instruction. Once you consider what 21st century skills students will need in order to engage in the meaningful tasks you have designed, consider which tools may help them to develop or showcase those skills. There are many virtual tools and EdTech websites used for teaching and learning. For the purpose of this study, the researchers would delimit it to Kahoot, Google classroom and Edmodo.

Kahoot is a learning tool that allows teachers and students to create fun games in order to test knowledge and engage the entire class. There is virtually no limit to the number of questions or their format; you could place videos, images, and even diagrams to each question to make the game more interesting (Atherton, 2018). Kahoot provides a learning environment that is ideal for engaging students for it to incorporate the

precepts of both game-based learning and inquiry-based learning. Kahoot allows teachers to create quizzes and surreys that include a wide variety of multimedia elements such as videos, pictures and text. Each quiz you create can be accessed by students across different devices. Also, teachers have the possibility to create time-controlled quizzes. You can set a specific period of time for the answer of each question. In this way students are rewarded not only for the correct answer but also for their timeliness.

Wang and Tahir's main conclusion on the effect of using Kahoot for learning is that Kahoot can have a positive effect on learning performance, classroom dynamics, students' and teachers' attitudes, and students' anxiety (Wang and Tahir, 2020). This type of learning experience can really keep the whole class engaged, as each student joins the game via their smart devices while the results appear on a shared screen for everyone to see. Forming multiple teams can build a competitive atmosphere which students would enjoy. In addition, the online nature of Kahoot allows you to include even those students that are unable to attend the class, but are willing to participate in the game. Furthermore, teachers could assign homework using this tool and have instant access to results. Kharbach (2021) asserted that Kahoot is a great student response system that teachers can use to create, deliver contents, assess and promote the 21st Century skills among students.

Licorish, Owen, Daniel and George (2018) found that Kahoot enriches the quality of students learning in the classroom, with the highest influence reported on classroom dynamics, engagement, motivation and improved learning experience. Our findings also suggest that the use of educational games in classrooms is likely to minimise distractions, thereby, improving the quality of teaching and learning beyond what is provided in conventional classrooms.

Another useful tool that not only makes the teaching experience easier but also helps integrate teachers, students, and parents in the learning process is Edmodo. Edmodo is a web-based platform that provides a safe and easy way for your class to connect and collaborate; share content, and access homework, grades and school notices. It is like Facebook but in a safe and controlled environment appropriate for school. Al-Essa (2018) stated that Edmodo allows teachers to create groups quizzes, assign papers, manage students' progress, etc. It's also possible to connect Edmodo with your Google or Microsoft account, and transfer files from one service to another seamlessly. Pardede (2017) identified various advantages of employing Edmodo for 21st century skills. Such includes its ability to facilitate intensive communication which is highly necessary in the global environment, its potential to assist for running

various types of active learning (e.g. provision of assignments and related resources, peer discussion, online quizzes concerning the learned topic, digital content assignment submission, and easy connection with students or teachers from different schools or other countries). Edmodo also facilitates teachers to meet the varied students' needs, supports a sense of community among students, making them feel respected and significant while offering three helpful criteria - usability, accessibility, and compatibility (Bayne, 2015).

This tool is a great way to keep parents up to date with future events, current grades, progress, etc. Since teachers can allow access to both students and parents, each user has a certain level of access to Edmodo content. This way, parents will be able to see where they should jump in when it comes to helping their children achieve better results. One of the amazing features of this tool is the ability to share any type of content with other users. Alqahtani (2019) showed that using Edmodo leads to a statistically significant improvement in learning skills among higher education students and develop vastly the acquisition of 21st century skills. The results also illustrate that students have positive attitudes toward the use of Edmodo in their courses.

Google Classroom is also an effective tool in improving teaching and learning. It works pretty simply; the teacher creates a class and invites students to join by sending them an invitation via Gmail. As the students join the class, they have instant access to all the materials that the teacher provides. Moreover, the teacher is able to create quizzes, assign essays, tests, and even create a class calendar with important dates so students stay updated always, and so on. The teacher has access to students' ongoing work and has the ability to provide insightful feedback. In a word, this tool is a virtual classroom that is always open.

Zulkefli, Hashim and Syahrin (2020) described Google Classroom as a stable platform for server or network. As long as students and teachers have access to the internet, videos and teaching materials are accessed instantaneously. The Google Classroom features include quiz, shared drive (where students and teachers can discuss in a real-time), and rubric for assignments. Other facilities are centralized Grading System and real-time sharing messages, as well as links to Google Drive and social repository (e.g., YouTube) for the storage of large files.

Google Classroom can be used at any grade (basic, post basic and tertiary) levels, but this depends on the teachers' and students' competence (Bell, 2015). Therefore, Google Classroom can be defined as a digital tool that enables students to attend

classes online. Teachers work together with their students without meeting face-to-face, post materials for their students make announcements and create assignments and quizzes for students to complete, submit and save online either in a web browser or on the Google Classroom App. This Google service allows teachers to organize their class, interact with students, grade their work, check on their progress, and much more. Due to its available on smart devices and only requires a Google account, Google Classroom ensures certain amount of flexibility to both teacher and students (Bell, 2015).

Studies by Mafa (2018) and Nizal, Shaharane, Jamil, Syamimi, and Rodzi, (2016) found out that Google Classroom is fascinating in educating and learning, and students' taught indicated satisfaction towards the learning activities in Google Classroom. Furthermore, Fahrurrozi, Hasanah and Dewi (2019) conducted a study to determine the requirements for the development of learning that is exciting, active, autonomous and effective. The results of the study showed that integrated learning design based on Google Classroom is needed to improve students' digital literacy and 21st century skills.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of virtual learning tools in classrooms on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century in Nigeria. Specifically, the study has the following objectives:

1. To establish the influence of **Kahoot** learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills.
2. To examine the influence of Edmodo learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills.
3. To examine the influence of **Google Classroom** learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the influence of **Kahoot** learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills?
2. What is the influence of Edmodo learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills?
3. What is the influence of **Google Classroom** learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills?

Hypotheses

Three hypotheses were postulated at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study. They are:

1. There is no significant influence of **Kahoot** learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills.
2. There is no significant influence of Edmodo learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills.
3. There is no significant influence of **Google Classroom** learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills.

Significance of the Study

This comparative study would expose teachers and students to the effectiveness of online education students' acquisition of 21st century skills. The study would help the government to improve on the teaching and learning through EdTech by organizing workshops, seminars and compulsory in-service programmes to educate teachers on the innovative teaching methods and appropriate strategies in teaching and provision of facilities to aid virtual learning.

Research Methods

Descriptive research design was adopted for this study, and undergraduate students in the Faculty of Education in both University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State and Abia State University, Uturu, Abia State made up the population.

The total population was 10,152 undergraduate students in the two institutions. A sample of 985 students was selected from the population through multi-stage and simple random sampling techniques for the study. Researchers-developed instrument titled "Virtual Learning Tools and 21st Century Skills Questionnaire" (VLT21stCSQ) was used in gathering data. The face validity of the instrument was carried out and the reliability coefficient .79 of the instrument was determined using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistical tool after a trial test method. Mean, Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Variance was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Data Analysis and Results

Research questions and hypotheses are answered alongside using the same table

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of **Kahoot** learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills.

Table 4: Mean, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the influence of Kahoot learning tools on students' acquisition of 21st century skills.

Variables	Students' Century Skills	21st N	Mean	SD
Kahoot Learning Tools	High	476	54.17	17.75
	Moderate	358	50.38	15.07
	Low	151	48.38	14.11

Sources of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F-Cal	F-Crit	Sig.	Decision at p?.05
Between groups	1330.44	2	665.22	5.68*	3.00	.004	Rejected
Within groups	114862.33	982	116.96				
Total	116192.77	984					

*= Significant at .05; N = 985

The result in table 4 shows that the mean score of students' acquisition of 21st century skills based on high rating of **Kahoot** learning tools is 54.17. Those under moderate rating have the mean 50.38, while those with low rating based on **Kahoot** learning tools have 48.38. This shows that students who acquire 21st century skills using **Kahoot** learning tools are more compared to moderate and low rating, respectively.

Also, the result reveals that the calculated F of 5.68 is greater than the critical F of 3.00 at 0.05 alpha levels with 2 and 982 degrees of freedom. Again, the p-value of .004 is less than the .05 levels of significance. This means that **Kahoot** learning tools influence undergraduate students, thereby, enhancing their acquisition of 21st century skills. This is an indication that the null hypothesis which speculated that there is no significant influence of **Kahoot** learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills in the University of Uyo and Abia State is rejected while the alternative is retained.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant influence of Edmodo learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills.

Table 5: Mean, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the influence of Edmodo learning tools on students' acquisition of 21st century skills.

Variables	Students' Skills	21st Century	N	SD
Edmodo Learning Tool	High		459	54.85
	Moderate		342	51.48
	Low		184	48.50

Sources of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F-Cal	F-Crit	Sig.	Decision at p? .05
Between groups	1846.78	2	923.39	7.93*	3.00	.002	Rejected
Within groups	114345.99	982	116.44				
Total	116192.77	984					

*= Significant at .05; N = 985

From the data on table 5, the mean score of students' acquisition of 21st century skills based on high rating of Edmodo learning tools is 54.85. Those under moderate rating is 51.48 while students who have low rating have the mean 48.50. This shows that students who acquire 21st century skills using Edmodo learning tools are more compared to moderate and low, respectively.

Also, the result reveals that the calculated F of 7.93 is greater than the critical F of 3.00 at 0.05 alpha levels with 2 and 982 degrees of freedom. Again, the p-value of .002 is less than the .05 levels of significance. This indicates that the null hypothesis which speculated that there is no significant influence of Edmodo learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills in the University of Uyo and Abia State University is rejected while the alternative is retained. This could be inferred that Edmodo learning tools significantly influence undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant influence of **Google Classroom** learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills.

Table 5: Mean, Standard Deviation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of the influence of Google classroom learning tools on students' acquisition of 21st century skills.

Variables	Students ' Skills	21st Century	N	SD
Google Classroom Learning Tool	High		403	53.16
	Moderate		326	50.06
	Low		256	47.39

Sources of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F-Cal	F-Crit	Sig.	Decision at p?.05
Between groups	1230.89	2	615.45	5.25*	3.00	.004	Rejected
Within groups	114961.87	982	117.06				
Total	116192.77	984					

*= Significant at .05; N = 985

The results in Table 6 shows that the mean score of students' acquisition of 21st century skills based on high rating of **Google Classroom** learning tool is 53.16. Those under moderate rating is 50.06, while students who have low rating based on the **Google Classroom** is 47.39. This shows that students who acquire 21st century skills using **Google Classroom** learning tools are more compared to moderate and low, respectively.

Also, the result reveals that the calculated F of 5.25 is greater than the critical F of 3.00 at 0.05 alpha levels with 2 and 982 degrees of freedom. Again, the p-value of .004 is less than the .05 levels of significance. This indicates that the null hypothesis which speculated that there is no significant influence of **Google Classroom** learning tools on undergraduate is rejected while the alternative is retained. This could be inferred that **Google classroom** learning tools significantly influences undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills.

Discussion of the Findings

Hypothesis one (1) showed that there is a significant influence of **Kahoot** learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills in the University of Uyo and Abia State University. The study also revealed that students who rated **Kahoot** learning tools high in the acquisition of 21st century skills are more. This result could be attributed to the fact that Kahoot learning tool allows teachers and students to create fun games in order to test knowledge and provides an ideal learning

environment for engaging students and the entire class. This makes learners more relaxed, excited, interested and ready to learn.

The result of this study is in agreement with earlier findings by Kharbach (2021) who asserted that Kahoot is a great student-response system that teachers can use to create, deliver contents, assess and promote the 21st Century skills among students. Also, Wang and Tahir (2020) concluded that Kahoot can have a positive effect on learning performance, classroom dynamics, students' and teachers' attitudes, and students' anxiety. This type of learning experience can really keep the whole class engaged, as each student joins the game via their smart devices while the results appear on a shared screen for everyone to see.

The findings of this study on hypothesis two showed that there is a significant influence of Edmodo learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills in the University of Uyo and Abia State University. The study also revealed that students who rated Edmodo learning tools high in the acquisition of 21st century skills are more. This result could be attributed to the fact that Edmodo learning tool makes it possible for students and teachers to connect with their Google or Microsoft account and transfer files, ideas, knowledge, skills among others and from one service to another seamlessly. Edmodo learning tool is a great way to keep parents up to date with future events, current grades, and progress of their wards.

The result of this study is in agreement with earlier findings by Bayne (2015) who affirmed that Edmodo facilitates teachers to meet the varied students' needs, supports a sense of community among students, making them feel respected and significant, and offers three helpful criteria, i.e., usability, accessibility, and compatibility. Also, Alqahtani (2019) research findings showed that using Edmodo leads to a statistically significant improvement in learning skills among higher education students and develop vastly the acquisition of 21st century skills. The results also illustrate that students have positive attitudes toward the use of Edmodo in their courses.

The findings of this study on hypothesis three showed that there is a significant influence of Google Classroom learning tools on undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills in the University of Uyo and Abia State University. The study also revealed that students who rated Google Classroom learning tools highest in the acquisition of 21st century skills are more. This result could be attributed to the fact that Google classroom learning tool is a stable platform for server or network. This Google service allows teachers to organize their class, interact with students, grade their work, check on their progress, and much more.

The result of this study was in agreement with earlier findings by Mafa, (2018) and Nizal, Shaharane, Jamil, Syamimi, and Rodzi (2016) found out that Google Classroom is fascinating in educating and learning, and students' taught indicated satisfaction towards the learning activities. Also, Fahrurrozi, Hasanah, Dewi (2019) study revealed that the Google Classroom provides for the development of learning that is exciting, active, autonomous and effective. And that integrated learning design based on Google classroom is needed to improve student digital literacy and 21st century skills.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that virtual learning tools in the classroom significantly influence undergraduate students' acquisition of 21st century skills. This has led to a shift in instructional delivery, students' participation and assessment toward technological approach through virtual learning. Based on the conclusions reached, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teachers should be dynamic in their approach to knowledge and skills acquisition and their utilization of varied technological approaches in teaching process. They should attain to individual need of students so as to carry everybody along in the teaching and learning process.
2. Teachers should use the virtual tools application such that the students enjoy the experience as they may find it useful to know that their teachers are supportive and willing to work with them in a positive and competitive environment.
3. In a global society, there is an innate need for students to become proficient in each of the 21st Century skills. When merged into and thread through instructional content, communication, collaboration, critical thinking and problem solving, and creativity are completely accessible and possible through a virtual environment.
4. Seminars, workshops and conferences should be organised by the Ministry of Education, Governments and NGOs to popularise the innovative and robust teaching via technological approaches to the teachers.

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